

Internal and Emergency Medicine

Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt Reduces Hospital Care Burden in patients with Decompensated Cirrhosis

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>Background and aims: Patients with decompensated cirrhosis frequently require hospital admissions, which are associated with worse prognosis. The aim of this study was to analyze the effect of TIPS on need for hospital care. Secondary objectives were to assess the clinical and biological impact of TIPS and to identify predictors of post-TIPS hospital care.</p> <p>Methods: An observational, retrospective study of patients with decompensated cirrhosis treated with TIPS from January 2008 until March 2019. Exclusion criteria were TIPS placed for non-cirrhotic portal hypertension (PH) and patients referred from another hospital without prior or subsequent follow-up at our Unit. Hospital care, PH-related complications and laboratory data were compared before and after TIPS.</p> <p>Results: The final cohort comprised 104 patients (72% male) with a mean age of 60 (± 10) years. Follow-up from first decompensation until TIPS and from procedure to study completion were 7 (4.2-9.8) and 20 (4.6-35.4) months, respectively. TIPS was indicated mainly for refractory ascites (50%) and variceal bleeding (39%). Hemodynamic and clinical success rates were 97% and 92%. The number of emergency department visits and hospital admissions decreased after the procedure ($p < 0.001$). Improvement was seen in MELD and Child-Pugh scores, renal function,</p>

	<p>hyponatremia and anemia after TIPS. Variceal bleeding as the indication for TIPS (OR=0.047; 95CI=0.006-0,39; p <0.05) together with early creation of the shunt (stage 3 vs 5; p<0.05) were associated with a reduction in risk of post-TIPS hospital care.</p> <p>Conclusion: TIPS is a safe and effective procedure that reduces hospital care burden by improving PH-related complications, hepatic, renal function, hyponatremia and anemia. Variceal bleeding as the indication and early placement of the device were associated with a reduction in post-TIPS hospital care. These findings support a role for this treatment, predominantly in the early stages of cirrhosis.</p>
Response to Reviewers:	Dear Editor, We have resubmitted a R2 version with all changes clearly indicated in the text and in the point-by-point letter. Thank you.

Response to Reviewers

Dear reviewers,

We appreciate the detailed review and all associated comments. We have made a major review with several modifications:

In response to reviewer 1:

- We clarify that cirrhosis decompensations, including hepatic encephalopathy, were diagnosed following the diagnostic criteria of clinical guidelines (page 7, second paragraph, red color).
- Ammonia levels were not available and therefore, not provided since their measurement was not performed routinely in the clinical practice of our department.

In response to reviewer 2:

- HCC patients were not excluded as they are part of the cirrhosis population that requires medical assistance and we wanted to show a real life scenario. Indeed, the sentence "to confirm... the absence of liver tumors" could create confusion. We have eliminated it (page 5, third paragraph).
- Information about comorbidities has not been included as it is not the objective of the study. However, we have clarified that only visits to the emergency department and hospital admissions secondary to any decompensations of cirrhosis were considered in the analyses. Other causes different from liver-related complications were excluded after a careful review of the medical records (page 7, second paragraph, underscored).
- We specify that "Sixteen (15%) patients were transplanted, 2 (2%) lost follow-up and 57 (55%) died during the study period" after TIPS (page 8).
- In the definition section it is explained that the clinical success was evaluated at the end of each patient's follow-up. Therefore, percentages of refractory ascites and HH resolution were maintained (page 6).
- We have rechecked cases of ACLF after TIPS and strictly applying the diagnostic criteria, the number of cases has been reduced (table 2). We have also added a subanalysis of factors that could influence hepatic encephalopathy in the results and discussion sections (page 11 and 13).
- We specify that also shunt-derived complications and dysfunction were considered in the global amount of post-TIPS hospital admissions and complications (page 6 and 7, underscored).
- Statistical analysis of the figures has been added (Figure 1).
- We have evaluated the influence of the etiological treatment of cirrhosis on the post-TIPS evolution (Table 4, red color).
- We have removed the sentence "No cases of hepatic failure were seen".
- Shunt complications (including ischemic hepatitis and congestive heart failure) are included in the analyses (Table 4, underscored).
- English language have been revised throughout the manuscript.

Thank you very much and we look forward to receive your response to our work.

Sincerely yours,
Maria Pilar Ballester.

TITLE PAGE:

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- i. **Title:** Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt Reduces Hospital Care Burden in patients with Decompensated Cirrhosis.
- ii. **Running Head:** TIPS Reduces Hospital Care in Cirrhosis.
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17 **v. Abstract:**
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19 Background and aims: Patients with decompensated cirrhosis frequently
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21 require hospital admissions, which are associated with worse prognosis. The aim
22
23 of this study was to analyze the effect of TIPS on need for hospital care. Secondary
24
25 objectives were to assess the clinical and biological impact of TIPS and to identify
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27 predictors of post-TIPS hospital care.
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31 Methods: An observational, retrospective study of patients with
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33 decompensated cirrhosis treated with TIPS from January 2008 until March 2019.
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35 Exclusion criteria were TIPS placed for non-cirrhotic portal hypertension (PH)
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37 and patients referred from another hospital without prior or subsequent follow-up
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39 at our Unit. Hospital care, PH-related complications and laboratory data were
40
41 compared before and after TIPS.
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46 Results: The final cohort comprised 104 patients (72% male) with a mean
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48 age of 60 (± 10) years. Follow-up from first decompensation until TIPS and from
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50 procedure to study completion were 7 (4.2-9.8) and 20 (4.6-35.4) months,
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52 respectively. TIPS was indicated mainly for refractory ascites (50%) and variceal
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54 bleeding (39%). Hemodynamic and clinical success rates were 97% and 92%. The
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56 number of emergency department visits and hospital admissions decreased after
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the procedure ($p<0.001$). Improvement was seen in MELD and Child-Pugh scores, renal function, hyponatremia and anemia after TIPS. Variceal bleeding as the indication for TIPS (OR=0.047; 95CI=0.006-0,39; $p<0.05$) together with early creation of the shunt (stage 3 vs 5; $p<0.05$) were associated with a reduction in risk of post-TIPS hospital care.

Conclusion: TIPS is a safe and effective procedure that reduces hospital care burden by improving PH-related complications, hepatic, renal function, hyponatremia and anemia. Variceal bleeding as the indication and early placement of the device were associated with a reduction in post-TIPS hospital care. These findings support a role for this treatment, predominantly in the early stages of cirrhosis.

vi. Key words: Liver Cirrhosis; Hypertension, Portal; Portosystemic Shunt, Transjugular Intrahepatic; Care, Medical.

vii. Declarations:

- **Funding:** The authors declare no financial support.
- **Conflicts of interest:** The authors declare no conflicts of interest.
- **Ethics approval:** The study protocol conformed to the ethical guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Health Research Ethics Board.
- **Authors contributions:** **Ballester MP and Lluch P:** designed the study. **Gómez C, Capilla M, Tosca J, Martí-Aguado D, Guijarro J and Rengel M:** acquired the data. **Ballester MP:** analyzed and interpreted the data and wrote the manuscript. **Lluch P and Minguez M:** performed a critical revision.

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2 **MAIN TEXT:**
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7 **Introduction**
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10 The natural history of cirrhosis is characterized by an asymptomatic phase over a
11 prolonged period followed by progressive development of portal hypertension (PH)
12 and/or liver dysfunction [1]. PH is the best surrogate marker associated with cirrhosis
13 complications that can negatively affect disease progression and survival [2].
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19 Transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS) is an established therapeutic
20 option to treat several PH-related complications such as variceal bleeding or refractory
21 ascites, and has been shown to improve transplant-free survival [3-7]. The main
22 complications of TIPS have traditionally been shunt stenosis and hepatic encephalopathy
23 (HE) [8-9]. Increased experience and technical developments such as covered stents have
24 led to improved shunt patency and clinical outcomes, resulting in an increased application
25 of this technique [10-11].
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36 Patients with decompensated cirrhosis frequently require medical care and hospital
37 admissions [12] which are associated with impaired prognosis, regardless of the stage of
38 cirrhosis [13]. In addition to its negative impact on life expectancy, decompensated
39 cirrhosis entails several other burdens, including a marked increase in healthcare costs
40 due to hospitalization, treatment and lost productivity [14]. Strategies such as improving
41 access to outpatient specialized care have therefore been proposed to reduce hospital
42 admissions and readmissions [15-16].
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53 We hypothesized that as a therapeutic tool in the management of PH-related
54 complications, TIPS would reduce the need for medical care in patients with
55 decompensated cirrhosis. The main aim of our study was to analyze the influence of TIPS
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1 on the need for emergency department care and hospitalization. Secondary objectives
2 were to (I) assess the clinical and biological impact of TIPS placement and (II) identify
3 prognostic predictors of post-TIPS hospital care.
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10 **Methods**

11 **Study design and patient selection**

12 An analytical retrospective study was performed in patients with cirrhosis and PH-
13 related complications treated with TIPS in the Hepatology Unit of the Clinic University
14 Hospital of Valencia. Cirrhosis diagnosis was based on liver histology or a combination
15 of clinical, biochemical and imaging signs. Exclusion criteria were: (I) TIPS placed for
16 non-cirrhotic PH and (II) patients referred from another hospital directly to the
17 Interventional Radiology department without prior or subsequent follow-up in our
18 Hepatology Unit. Patients were consecutively registered in a database from January 2008
19 to March 2019. Epidemiological, clinical and procedural data were retrospectively
20 acquired from medical history records.
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36 **Pre-TIPS evaluation, TIPS creation and monitoring**

37 The indications for TIPS were evaluated following clinical guidelines [3-4, 17-18].
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39 All patients underwent a pre-TIPS examination that included clinical evaluation (age, sex,
40 etiology of cirrhosis, evidence of previous or current liver decompensation, indication for
41 TIPS and urgency of the procedure), laboratory study (serum electrolytes, kidney and
42 hepatic function tests and blood counts) and cross-sectional liver imaging by Doppler-
43 ultrasound, computed tomography scan or magnetic resonance imaging to assess portal
44 vein patency or presence of liver tumors. Cardiac evaluation was performed in all
45 scheduled procedures with echocardiography and additional cardiology consultation
46 when there was a history of congestive heart failure, tricuspid regurgitation,
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1 cardiomyopathy or pulmonary hypertension. Model for End stage Liver Disease (MELD)
2 [19] and Child-Pugh [20] scores were used to predict survival following TIPS procedure.
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4 We also used a 5-clinical stage classification of cirrhosis according to presence of
5 complications and risk of progression to further decompensation, liver failure or death
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7 [21].
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11 TIPS placement was carried out by an interventional radiologist following the Society
12 of Interventional Radiology guidelines [22-24]. Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) covered
13 stents (Viatorr®) were used in all cases. Shunt diameter varied between 8 to 10 mm and
14 length from 5 to 10 cm. All technical or shunt-derived complications were recorded. TIPS
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16 dysfunction was treated with balloon dilation or re-stenting.
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24 Clinical surveillance was performed at 1, 3 and 6 months after TIPS creation and then
25 every 6 months thereafter, with blood test and doppler ultrasonography, unless clinical
26 deterioration occurred, until liver transplantation, loss to follow-up, death or study closure
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28 in March 2020.
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33 **Definitions**

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35 Technical success was defined as the creation of a shunt between the hepatic vein and
36 a branch of the portal vein [22-24]. Hemodynamic success refers to reduction of the
37 portosystemic gradient (PSG) to 12 mmHg or lower, or reducing the initial value by at
38 least 20% [22-24]. Clinical effectiveness was defined by resolution of the clinical
39 indication for the procedure (cessation of variceal bleeding, decrease of
40 ascites/hydrothorax and conversion into diuretic-sensitive ascites/hydrothorax or
41 improvement of liver function) [22-24] and was decided at the end of each patient's
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43 follow-up.
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1 TIPS dysfunction was defined as a loss of decompression of the portal venous system
2 due to occlusion or stenosis of the stent [18]. It was evaluated at any time during follow-
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4 up.
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7 As the primary endpoint, need for hospital care was evaluated as number of visits to
8 the emergency department and hospital admissions before and after the TIPS procedure,
9 including only medical visits made for any type of decompensation of cirrhosis or TIPS-
10 derived complication. Cirrhosis decompensations were diagnosed following the
11 diagnostic criteria of clinical guidelines [17]. Medical care required for other
12 comorbidities was not included.
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21 **Statistical analysis**

22 Descriptive statistics were used to characterize demographics of the study population
23 and TIPS procedures. Distribution of the continuous variables was obtained by the
24 Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Normally and non-normally distributed variables were
25 expressed as mean and standard deviation (SD) or as median and interquartile range
26 (IQR), respectively. Categorical variables were expressed as absolute frequencies and
27 percentages (%).
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38 Follow-up periods were calculated with Kaplan-Meier survival analysis and
39 compared with the log-rank test.
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43 Changes in continuous variables after TIPS creation were analyzed with a paired
44 samples t-test and the Wilcoxon test. The McNemar test was used to compared changes
45 in qualitative variables.
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50 Univariate analysis was performed to study baseline characteristics according to post-
51 TIPS need for hospital care. Either chi-square test or Fisher test were performed with
52 qualitative variables. Measures of association between qualitative variables were reported
53 as odds ratio (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (95CI). Between-group comparison of
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1 quantitative variables was made with the t-test, Mann-Whitney U test or Kruskal–Wallis
2 test, as required. Variables with a *p* value <0.10 from the univariate analysis were
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4 introduced in a multivariate logistic regression analysis to identify confounding factors
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6 for post-TIPS medical care.
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9 A two-tailed *p*-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Analyses were
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11 performed with the SPSS V22.0 software package.
12

13 **Ethics**

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15 The study protocol conformed to the ethical guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki
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17 and was approved by the Health Research Ethics Board.
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23 **Results**

24 **Study population**

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26 A total of 109 patients underwent TIPS in our department during the study period.
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28 Five patients were excluded due to non-cirrhotic PH (n=1) or lack of follow-up in our
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30 unit (n=4), leaving a final cohort of 104 patients whose baseline characteristics are
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32 summarized in Table 1.
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39 Median follow-up from first decompensation to TIPS creation was 7 (95CI=4.2-9.8)
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41 months (Supplementary figure 1A) while from TIPS to the end of the study was 20
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43 (95CI=4.6-35.4) months (Supplementary figure 1B). Sixteen (15%) patients were
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45 transplanted, 2 (2%) lost to follow-up and 57 (55%) died after TIPS during the study
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47 period.
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50 **TIPS procedure and procedure-related complications**

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52 Technical success was achieved in all cases. Hemodynamic effectiveness was seen in
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54 101 (97%) procedures. Mean PSG fell substantially after the procedure, from 20 (5.1) to
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56 7.9 (2.3) mmHg (-12.3 mmHg ± 4.9; 95CI=11-13; *p*<0.001). Clinical success was
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2 achieved in 96 (92%) patients. Resolution of refractory ascites, variceal bleeding and HH
3 was observed in 45 (87%), 40 (100%) and 6 (100%) cases, respectively.

4
5 There were two (1.9%) technical complications: a hepatic capsule puncture that was
6 successfully managed conservatively and a shunt created between the suprahepatic vein
7 and the hepatic artery that was closed with an Amplatzer® vascular device. Regarding
8 shunt-derived complications, mild ischemic hepatitis and congestive heart failure
9 occurred in 12 (11.5%) and 7 (7.7%) patients, all transitory and managed with medical
10 treatment without the need for TIPS closure. Shunt dysfunction was seen in 17 (16.3%)
11 cases, six (35%) of which appeared during the first month after the procedure. All cases
12 were successfully treated by balloon dilation or re-stenting in series with no impact on
13 clinical efficacy (OR=0.29; 95CI=0.06-1.33; $p=0.121$).

24 25 26 **Hospital care requirements and impact of TIPS**

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28 Median emergency department visits decreased significantly from 3 (2-6) pre-TIPS
29 to 1 (0-3) post-TIPS ($p<0.001$). Hospital admissions also decreased after TIPS from a
30 median of 3 (2-4) to 1 (0-2) ($p<0.001$).

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32 The effect of TIPS on cirrhosis complications prompting medical care is specified in
33 Table 2.

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35 Compared to baseline, the MELD score was worse during the first month (mean of
36 16 ± 5.7 ; $p<0.001$), followed by progressive improvement at 6 and 12 months (mean of
37 14 ± 5.6 , $p=0.233$ and 13 ± 6.1 , $p=0.606$, respectively) (Figure 1A). The Child-Pugh score
38 followed a similar course (mean of 8.2 ± 2.0 , $p=0.383$ during the first month; 7.2 ± 1.8 ,
39 $p=0.052$ at 6 months; and 6.8 ± 1.5 , $p<0.005$ at 12 months compared to baseline) (Figure
40 1B).

41
42 Similarly, liver function parameters worsened during the first month after TIPS, with
43 subsequent improvement throughout the first year. Renal function improved, showing
44

1 lower levels of creatinine over time and normalized hyponatremia. Hemoglobin levels
2 also increased during follow-up (Table 3).
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4 **Prognostic predictors of post-TIPS hospital care**

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7 Factors associated with a need for post-TIPS medical care are specified in Table 4.
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9 Older age was a risk factor for post-TIPS hospital admissions (61 ± 10 vs 57 ± 10 years
10 old; $p=0.044$). Alcoholic cirrhosis was associated with reduced post-TIPS hospital care
11 requirements (44% vs 71%; OR=0.32; 95CI=0.14-0.75; $p=0.008$); however, alcoholic
12 plus HCV cirrhosis increased the risk for emergency care after the procedure (24% vs
13 8%; OR=3.7; 95CI=1.01-13.8; $p=0.038$).
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21 Refractory ascites as the indication for TIPS was associated with post-TIPS need for
22 both urgent medical care (61% vs 29%; OR=4.03; 95CI=1.7-9.5; $p=0.001$) and hospital
23 admissions (58% vs 39%; OR=2.2; 95CI= 1.004-4.9; $p=0.047$). In contrast, variceal
24 bleeding -as well as the urgency of the procedure- was associated with a reduced risk of
25 visits to the emergency department (23% vs 66%; OR=0.15; 95CI=0.06-0.4; $p=0.000$)
26 and hospital admissions (27% vs 54%; OR=0.303; 95CI=0.13-0.7; $p=0.004$). Early stages
27 of decompensated cirrhosis have been shown to reduce the need for urgent care (12% vs
28 32%; OR=0.29; 95CI=0.11-0.82; $p=0.015$) while advanced stage has been found to be a
29 risk factor (76 vs 55%; OR=2.5; 95CI=1.1-5.9; $p=0.031$).
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43 Multivariate logistic regression analysis included etiology and stage of cirrhosis and
44 the indication for TIPS to evaluate post-TIPS emergency department visits; and age,
45 etiology of cirrhosis and the indication for TIPS to assess hospital admissions. In this
46 analysis only variceal bleeding as the cause remained a protective factor against post-
47 TIPS medical care requirements (Table 5).
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55 Median follow-up after TIPS was 13 ± 7.5 months in the variceal bleeding group and
56 9 ± 10.8 months in the refractory ascites group ($p=0.947$). Only 28% of patients whose
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1 TIPS were due to variceal bleeding pertained to clinical stage 5 while all TIPS for
2 refractory ascites were in that group ($p<0.001$). Similarly, the Child-Pugh score was lower
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4 in the variceal bleeding group than in the refractory ascites one (mean of 8 ± 2 vs 9 ± 2 ;
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7 $p=0.022$), without differences in the MELD score ($p=0.805$).

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9 Post-TIPS visits to the emergency department and hospital admissions were not
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11 correlated with either hemodynamic or clinical effectiveness nor with technical, shunt-
12
13 related complications or TIPS dysfunction (Table 4).

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15 Focusing on HE as the most common precipitant of medical care after TIPS, variceal
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17 bleeding proved to be a protective factor against its development, compared to refractory
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19 ascites (33% vs 60%; OR=0.326; 95CI=0.14-0.77; $p=0.010$). In contrast, risk of post-
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21 TIPS HE increased in the advanced stages of cirrhosis (9.1% vs 12.7% vs 78.2% in stages
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24 3, 4 and 5 respectively; $p=0.007$).

25 26 27 28 29 30 31 **Discussion**

32
33 In this study, we have demonstrated that TIPS reduces the need for medical attention
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35 in patients with cirrhosis and PH-related complications by cutting in half the number of
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37 visits to the emergency department and hospital admissions.

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39 During the asymptomatic phase of cirrhosis, disease may go undetected for many
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41 years. However, disease progression is marked by development of clinical signs and
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43 symptoms which may impair quality of life [1]. As shown in this study, the most common
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45 first decompensations are ascites, variceal bleeding, HE and jaundice. Following the
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47 appearance of any of these complications, disease usually progresses rapidly towards
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49 liver transplant or death; the median follow-up in our cohort before TIPS was 3 (0-8)
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51 years, while the decompensated phase of cirrhosis lasted only 7 (1-32) months.
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2 To compare the hospital-based care burden before and after TIPS, we considered only
3 this shorter, symptomatic phase of cirrhosis. Therefore, the post-TIPS time frame was
4 comparable to or even longer than the pre-TIPS period, further supporting a relative time-
5 related decrease in the number of emergency department visits and hospital admissions
6 after TIPS creation.
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11 Previous studies demonstrated that hospital admissions reduce 1- and 5-year survival
12 probability, regardless of the stage of cirrhosis [13]. As we have shown, TIPS could be a
13 useful tool in patients with decompensated cirrhosis to diminish hospitalization and its
14 associated consequences.
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21 In patients with cirrhosis and recurrent ascites, a meta-analysis of individual patient
22 data [6] as well as a more recent randomized controlled trial [7] evidenced that TIPS with
23 covered stents increases transplant-free survival compared with patients undergoing
24 repeated large-volume paracentesis plus albumin, by lowering the total number of
25 paracenteses and episodes of PH-related bleeding or abdominal hernia-related
26 complications, and halving total hospital stays. In our cohort, refractory ascites as the
27 indication for TIPS was associated with higher Child-Pugh score. This could be explained
28 by the presence of ascites as one of its subjective components; however, it was also linked
29 to advanced stage of cirrhosis and higher rate of post-TIPS HE. Previous evidence
30 supporting the use of TIPS in patients with recurrent ascites, along with our worse
31 outcomes in patients with advanced cirrhosis and refractory ascites, show that covered
32 TIPS should be used as first-line intervention in patients with cirrhosis and not just
33 refractory but also recurrent ascites.
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52 Likewise, variceal bleeding as an indication for TIPS was associated with a reduction
53 in post-procedure hospital care, without significant differences in follow-up compared
54 with other indications. The urgency of the procedure, together with the lower stage of
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cirrhosis in this group, may have a bearing on this improved post-TIPS course of the disease.

As the main precipitants of TIPS, ascites and variceal bleeding incidence decreased substantially after shunt creation. Furthermore, we observed a non-statistically significant reduction in episodes of HRS and spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP). As expected from previous studies [8-9], the HE rate significantly increased; nonetheless, this was easily managed with pharmacological treatment in all patients and no TIPS closures were required. Factors associated with a lower risk of post-TIPS HE were again the indication of variceal bleeding and a reduced stage of cirrhosis, supporting early use of TIPS to avoid its more frequent complications.

Additionally, in agreement with other results [25-28], TIPS has been shown to improve both hepatic and renal function and normalize hyponatremia. In an interesting finding, hemoglobin levels have been shown to rise after TIPS placement, which may point to another indication for TIPS in less common PH complications such as chronic anemia due to PHG and gastric antral vascular ectasia, with their associated health care burden.

One limitation of the present study was its observational and retrospective methodology, which tends towards information bias and confounding variables. We attempted to diminish potential confounding factors by carefully and reliably reviewing medical records and conducting multivariate analyses. Secondly, the long inclusion period may imply changes in TIPS technique over time, although the success rates and complications related to the procedure were similar to previous studies [22-24]. Moreover, more experienced radiologists and optimal candidate selection have been associated with a decrease in the rate of complications and increased use over time.

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In summary, TIPS influences the clinical course of cirrhosis by reducing the number of emergency department visits and hospital admissions. In our cohort, TIPS was a safe procedure with a high success rate that led to a reduction of most PH-related complications, along with an improvement in hepatic and renal function, hyponatremia and anemia. Variceal bleeding as the indication for TIPS, together with a prompt procedure in patients with early stage cirrhosis, was associated with a lower post-TIPS hospital care burden. This indicates a key role for TIPS, particularly in the early stages of cirrhosis, which may provide a window of opportunity to modify the natural history of the disease.

In our view the results of this study could have an important impact on clinical practice. We propose earlier and expanded considerations of TIPS for managing PH-related complications as a strategy to reduce hospital-based care in this group of patients.

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Figures

- Figure 1. Boxplot showing variations in MELD (A) and Child-Pugh (B) scores over the first year after TIPS placement: paired samples t-test.

Supplementary figures:

- Supplementary figure 1. Time of follow-up from first decompensation to TIPS creation (A) and from procedure to the end of the study (B).

Tables

- Table 1. Baseline characteristics of study patients.
- Table 2. Pre- and post-TIPS complications of cirrhosis: McNemar test.
- Table 3. Laboratory baseline levels and variations over the first year after TIPS placement: paired samples t-test and Wilcoxon test.
- Table 4. Characteristics of study population according to post-TIPS hospital care: univariate analysis.
- Table 5. Predictive factors of post-TIPS medical care: multivariate logistic regression analysis.

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- i. **Title:** Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt Reduces Hospital Care Burden in patients with Decompensated Cirrhosis.
 - ii. **Running Head:** TIPS Reduces Hospital Care in Cirrhosis.
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v. Abstract:

Background and aims: Patients with decompensated cirrhosis frequently require hospital admissions, which are associated with worse prognosis. The aim of this study was to analyze the effect of TIPS on need for hospital care. Secondary objectives were to assess the clinical and biological impact of TIPS and to identify predictors of post-TIPS hospital care.

Methods: An observational, retrospective study of patients with decompensated cirrhosis treated with TIPS from January 2008 until March 2019. Exclusion criteria were TIPS placed for non-cirrhotic portal hypertension (PH) and patients referred from another hospital without prior or subsequent follow-up at our Unit. Hospital care, PH-related complications and laboratory data were compared before and after TIPS.

Results: The final cohort comprised 104 patients (72% male) with a mean age of 60 (± 10) years. Follow-up from first decompensation until TIPS and from procedure to study completion were 7 (4.2-9.8) and 20 (4.6-35.4) months, respectively. TIPS was indicated mainly for refractory ascites (50%) and variceal bleeding (39%). Hemodynamic and clinical success rates were 97% and 92%. The number of emergency department visits and hospital admissions decreased after

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the procedure ($p<0.001$). Improvement was seen in MELD and Child-Pugh scores, renal function, hyponatremia and anemia after TIPS. Variceal bleeding as the indication for TIPS (OR=0.047; 95CI=0.006-0,39; $p<0.05$) together with early creation of the shunt (stage 3 vs 5; $p<0.05$) were associated with a reduction in risk of post-TIPS hospital care.

Conclusion: TIPS is a safe and effective procedure that reduces hospital care burden by improving PH-related complications, hepatic, renal function, hyponatremia and anemia. Variceal bleeding as the indication and early placement of the device were associated with a reduction in post-TIPS hospital care. These findings support a role for this treatment, predominantly in the early stages of cirrhosis.

vi. Key words: Liver Cirrhosis; Hypertension, Portal; Portosystemic Shunt, Transjugular Intrahepatic; Care, Medical.

vii. Declarations:

- **Funding:** The authors declare no financial support.
- **Conflicts of interest:** The authors declare no conflicts of interest.
- **Ethics approval:** The study protocol conformed to the ethical guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the Health Research Ethics Board.
- **Authors contributions:** **Ballester MP and Lluch P:** designed the study. **Gómez C, Capilla M, Tosca J, Martí-Aguado D, Guijarro J and Rengel M:** acquired the data. **Ballester MP:** analyzed and interpreted the data and wrote the manuscript. **Lluch P and Minguez M:** performed a critical revision.

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2 **MAIN TEXT:**
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7 **Introduction**
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10 The natural history of cirrhosis is characterized by an asymptomatic phase over a
11 prolonged period followed by progressive development of portal hypertension (PH)
12 and/or liver dysfunction [1]. PH is the best surrogate marker associated with cirrhosis
13 complications that can negatively affect disease progression and survival [2].
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19 Transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt (TIPS) is an established therapeutic
20 option to treat several PH-related complications such as variceal bleeding or refractory
21 ascites, and has been shown to improve transplant-free survival [3-7]. The main
22 complications of TIPS have traditionally been shunt stenosis and hepatic encephalopathy
23 (HE) [8-9]. Increased experience and technical developments such as covered stents have
24 led to improved shunt patency and clinical outcomes, resulting in an increased application
25 of this technique [10-11].
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36 Patients with decompensated cirrhosis frequently require medical care and hospital
37 admissions [12] which are associated with impaired prognosis, regardless of the stage of
38 cirrhosis [13]. In addition to its negative impact on life expectancy, decompensated
39 cirrhosis entails several other burdens, including a marked increase in healthcare costs
40 due to hospitalization, treatment and lost productivity [14]. Strategies such as improving
41 access to outpatient specialized care have therefore been proposed to reduce hospital
42 admissions and readmissions [15-16].
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53 We hypothesized that as a therapeutic tool in the management of PH-related
54 complications, TIPS would reduce the need for medical care in patients with
55 decompensated cirrhosis. The main aim of our study was to analyze the influence of TIPS
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1 on the need for emergency department care and hospitalization. Secondary objectives
2 were to (I) assess the clinical and biological impact of TIPS placement and (II) identify
3 prognostic predictors of post-TIPS hospital care.
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9 **Methods**

10 **Study design and patient selection**

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12 An analytical retrospective study was performed in patients with cirrhosis and PH-
13 related complications treated with TIPS in the Hepatology Unit of the Clinic University
14 Hospital of Valencia. Cirrhosis diagnosis was based on liver histology or a combination
15 of clinical, biochemical and imaging signs. Exclusion criteria were: (I) TIPS placed for
16 non-cirrhotic PH and (II) patients referred from another hospital directly to the
17 Interventional Radiology department without prior or subsequent follow-up in our
18 Hepatology Unit. Patients were consecutively registered in a database from January 2008
19 to March 2019. Epidemiological, clinical and procedural data were retrospectively
20 acquired from medical history records.
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36 **Pre-TIPS evaluation, TIPS creation and monitoring**

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38 The indications for TIPS were evaluated following clinical guidelines [3-4, 17-18].
39 All patients underwent a pre-TIPS examination that included clinical evaluation (age, sex,
40 etiology of cirrhosis, evidence of previous or current liver decompensation, indication for
41 TIPS and urgency of the procedure), laboratory study (serum electrolytes, kidney and
42 hepatic function tests and blood counts) and cross-sectional liver imaging by Doppler-
43 ultrasound, computed tomography scan or magnetic resonance imaging to assess portal
44 vein patency or **presence of liver tumors**. Cardiac evaluation was performed in all
45 scheduled procedures with echocardiography and additional cardiology consultation
46 when there was a history of congestive heart failure, tricuspid regurgitation,
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1 cardiomyopathy or pulmonary hypertension. Model for End stage Liver Disease (MELD)
2 [19] and Child-Pugh [20] scores were used to predict survival following TIPS procedure.
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4 We also used a 5-clinical stage classification of cirrhosis according to presence of
5 complications and risk of progression to further decompensation, liver failure or death
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7 [21].
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11 TIPS placement was carried out by an interventional radiologist following the Society
12 of Interventional Radiology guidelines [22-24]. Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) covered
13 stents (Viatorr®) were used in all cases. Shunt diameter varied between 8 to 10 mm and
14 length from 5 to 10 cm. All technical or shunt-derived complications were recorded. TIPS
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16 dysfunction was treated with balloon dilation or re-stenting.
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24 Clinical surveillance was performed at 1, 3 and 6 months after TIPS creation and then
25 every 6 months thereafter, with blood test and doppler ultrasonography, unless clinical
26 deterioration occurred, until liver transplantation, loss to follow-up, death or study closure
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30 in March 2020.
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33 **Definitions**

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36 Technical success was defined as the creation of a shunt between the hepatic vein and
37 a branch of the portal vein [22-24]. Hemodynamic success refers to reduction of the
38 portosystemic gradient (PSG) to 12 mmHg or lower, or reducing the initial value by at
39 least 20% [22-24]. Clinical effectiveness was defined by resolution of the clinical
40 indication for the procedure (cessation of variceal bleeding, decrease of
41 ascites/hydrothorax and conversion into diuretic-sensitive ascites/hydrothorax or
42 improvement of liver function) [22-24] and was decided at the end of each patient's
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53 follow-up.
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1 TIPS dysfunction was defined as a loss of decompression of the portal venous system
2 due to occlusion or stenosis of the stent [18]. It was evaluated at any time during follow-
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4 up.
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7 As the primary endpoint, need for hospital care was evaluated as number of visits to
8 the emergency department and hospital admissions before and after the TIPS procedure,
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10 including only medical visits made for any type of decompensation of cirrhosis or TIPS-
11 derived complication. Cirrhosis decompensations were diagnosed following the
12 diagnostic criteria of clinical guidelines [17]. Medical care required for other
13 comorbidities was not included.
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21 **Statistical analysis**

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23 Descriptive statistics were used to characterize demographics of the study population
24 and TIPS procedures. Distribution of the continuous variables was obtained by the
25 Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. Normally and non-normally distributed variables were
26 expressed as mean and standard deviation (SD) or as median and interquartile range
27 (IQR), respectively. Categorical variables were expressed as absolute frequencies and
28 percentages (%).
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38 Follow-up periods were calculated with Kaplan-Meier survival analysis and
39 compared with the log-rank test.
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42 Changes in continuous variables after TIPS creation were analyzed with a paired
43 samples t-test and the Wilcoxon test. The McNemar test was used to compared changes
44 in qualitative variables.
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50 Univariate analysis was performed to study baseline characteristics according to post-
51 TIPS need for hospital care. Either chi-square test or Fisher test were performed with
52 qualitative variables. Measures of association between qualitative variables were reported
53 as odds ratio (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (95CI). Between-group comparison of
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1 quantitative variables was made with the t-test, Mann-Whitney U test or Kruskal–Wallis
2 test, as required. Variables with a *p* value <0.10 from the univariate analysis were
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4 introduced in a multivariate logistic regression analysis to identify confounding factors
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6 for post-TIPS medical care.
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9 A two-tailed *p*-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Analyses were
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11 performed with the SPSS V22.0 software package.
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13 **Ethics**

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15 The study protocol conformed to the ethical guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki
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17 and was approved by the Health Research Ethics Board.
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23 **Results**

24 **Study population**

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26 A total of 109 patients underwent TIPS in our department during the study period.
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28 Five patients were excluded due to non-cirrhotic PH (n=1) or lack of follow-up in our
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30 unit (n=4), leaving a final cohort of 104 patients whose baseline characteristics are
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32 summarized in Table 1.
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38 Median follow-up from first decompensation to TIPS creation was 7 (95CI=4.2-9.8)
39
40 months (Supplementary figure 1A) while from TIPS to the end of the study was 20
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42 (95CI=4.6-35.4) months (Supplementary figure 1B). **Sixteen (15%) patients were**
43
44 **transplanted, 2 (2%) lost to follow-up and 57 (55%) died after TIPS during the study**
45
46 **period.**
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51 **TIPS procedure and procedure-related complications**

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53 Technical success was achieved in all cases. Hemodynamic effectiveness was seen in
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55 101 (97%) procedures. Mean PSG fell substantially after the procedure, from 20 (5.1) to
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57 7.9 (2.3) mmHg (-12.3 mmHg ± 4.9; 95CI=11-13; *p*<0.001). Clinical success was
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2 achieved in 96 (92%) patients. Resolution of refractory ascites, variceal bleeding and HH
3 was observed in 45 (87%), 40 (100%) and 6 (100%) cases, respectively.

4
5 There were two (1.9%) technical complications: a hepatic capsule puncture that was
6 successfully managed conservatively and a shunt created between the suprahepatic vein
7 and the hepatic artery that was closed with an Amplatzer® vascular device. Regarding
8 shunt-derived complications, mild ischemic hepatitis and congestive heart failure
9 occurred in 12 (11.5%) and 7 (7.7%) patients, all transitory and managed with medical
10 treatment without the need for TIPS closure. Shunt dysfunction was seen in 17 (16.3%)
11 cases, six (35%) of which appeared during the first month after the procedure. All cases
12 were successfully treated by balloon dilation or re-stenting in series with no impact on
13 clinical efficacy (OR=0.29; 95CI=0.06-1.33; $p=0.121$).

24 25 26 **Hospital care requirements and impact of TIPS**

27
28 Median emergency department visits decreased significantly from 3 (2-6) pre-TIPS
29 to 1 (0-3) post-TIPS ($p<0.001$). Hospital admissions also decreased after TIPS from a
30 median of 3 (2-4) to 1 (0-2) ($p<0.001$).

31
32 The effect of TIPS on cirrhosis complications prompting medical care is specified in
33 Table 2.

34
35 Compared to baseline, the MELD score was worse during the first month (mean of
36 16 ± 5.7 ; $p<0.001$), followed by progressive improvement at 6 and 12 months (mean of
37 14 ± 5.6 , $p=0.233$ and 13 ± 6.1 , $p=0.606$, respectively) (Figure 1A). The Child-Pugh score
38 followed a similar course (mean of 8.2 ± 2.0 , $p=0.383$ during the first month; 7.2 ± 1.8 ,
39 $p=0.052$ at 6 months; and 6.8 ± 1.5 , $p<0.005$ at 12 months compared to baseline) (Figure
40 1B).

41
42 Similarly, liver function parameters worsened during the first month after TIPS, with
43 subsequent improvement throughout the first year. Renal function improved, showing
44

1 lower levels of creatinine over time and normalized hyponatremia. Hemoglobin levels
2 also increased during follow-up (Table 3).
3

4 **Prognostic predictors of post-TIPS hospital care**

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7 Factors associated with a need for post-TIPS medical care are specified in Table 4.
8
9 Older age was a risk factor for post-TIPS hospital admissions (61 ± 10 vs 57 ± 10 years
10 old; $p=0.044$). Alcoholic cirrhosis was associated with reduced post-TIPS hospital care
11 requirements (44% vs 71%; OR=0.32; 95CI=0.14-0.75; $p=0.008$); however, alcoholic
12 plus HCV cirrhosis increased the risk for emergency care after the procedure (24% vs
13 8%; OR=3.7; 95CI=1.01-13.8; $p=0.038$).
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21 Refractory ascites as the indication for TIPS was associated with post-TIPS need for
22 both urgent medical care (61% vs 29%; OR=4.03; 95CI=1.7-9.5; $p=0.001$) and hospital
23 admissions (58% vs 39%; OR=2.2; 95CI= 1.004-4.9; $p=0.047$). In contrast, variceal
24 bleeding -as well as the urgency of the procedure- was associated with a reduced risk of
25 visits to the emergency department (23% vs 66%; OR=0.15; 95CI=0.06-0.4; $p=0.000$)
26 and hospital admissions (27% vs 54%; OR=0.303; 95CI=0.13-0.7; $p=0.004$). Early stages
27 of decompensated cirrhosis have been shown to reduce the need for urgent care (12% vs
28 32%; OR=0.29; 95CI=0.11-0.82; $p=0.015$) while advanced stage has been found to be a
29 risk factor (76 vs 55%; OR=2.5; 95CI=1.1-5.9; $p=0.031$).
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43 Multivariate logistic regression analysis included etiology and stage of cirrhosis and
44 the indication for TIPS to evaluate post-TIPS emergency department visits; and age,
45 etiology of cirrhosis and the indication for TIPS to assess hospital admissions. In this
46 analysis only variceal bleeding as the cause remained a protective factor against post-
47 TIPS medical care requirements (Table 5).
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55 Median follow-up after TIPS was 13 ± 7.5 months in the variceal bleeding group and
56 9 ± 10.8 months in the refractory ascites group ($p=0.947$). Only 28% of patients whose
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1 TIPS were due to variceal bleeding pertained to clinical stage 5 while all TIPS for
2 refractory ascites were in that group ($p<0.001$). Similarly, the Child-Pugh score was lower
3
4 in the variceal bleeding group than in the refractory ascites one (mean of 8 ± 2 vs 9 ± 2 ;
5
6
7 $p=0.022$), without differences in the MELD score ($p=0.805$).

8
9 Post-TIPS visits to the emergency department and hospital admissions were not
10
11 correlated with either hemodynamic or clinical effectiveness nor with technical, shunt-
12
13 related complications or TIPS dysfunction (Table 4).

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17 Focusing on HE as the most common precipitant of medical care after TIPS, variceal
18
19 bleeding proved to be a protective factor against its development, compared to refractory
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21 ascites (33% vs 60%; OR=0.326; 95CI=0.14-0.77; $p=0.010$). In contrast, risk of post-
22
23 TIPS HE increased in the advanced stages of cirrhosis (9.1% vs 12.7% vs 78.2% in stages
24
25 3, 4 and 5 respectively; $p=0.007$).

31 Discussion

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34 In this study, we have demonstrated that TIPS reduces the need for medical attention
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36 in patients with cirrhosis and PH-related complications by cutting in half the number of
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38 visits to the emergency department and hospital admissions.

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41 During the asymptomatic phase of cirrhosis, disease may go undetected for many
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43 years. However, disease progression is marked by development of clinical signs and
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45 symptoms which may impair quality of life [1]. As shown in this study, the most common
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47 first decompensations are ascites, variceal bleeding, HE and jaundice. Following the
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49 appearance of any of these complications, disease usually progresses rapidly towards
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51 liver transplant or death; the median follow-up in our cohort before TIPS was 3 (0-8)
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53 years, while the decompensated phase of cirrhosis lasted only 7 (1-32) months.
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1 To compare the hospital-based care burden before and after TIPS, we considered only
2 this shorter, symptomatic phase of cirrhosis. Therefore, the post-TIPS time frame was
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4 comparable to or even longer than the pre-TIPS period, further supporting a relative time-
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6 related decrease in the number of emergency department visits and hospital admissions
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8 after TIPS creation.
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11 Previous studies demonstrated that hospital admissions reduce 1- and 5-year survival
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13 probability, regardless of the stage of cirrhosis [13]. As we have shown, TIPS could be a
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15 useful tool in patients with decompensated cirrhosis to diminish hospitalization and its
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17 associated consequences.
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21 In patients with cirrhosis and recurrent ascites, a meta-analysis of individual patient
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23 data [6] as well as a more recent randomized controlled trial [7] evidenced that TIPS with
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25 covered stents increases transplant-free survival compared with patients undergoing
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27 repeated large-volume paracentesis plus albumin, by lowering the total number of
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29 paracenteses and episodes of PH-related bleeding or abdominal hernia-related
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31 complications, and halving total hospital stays. In our cohort, refractory ascites as the
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33 indication for TIPS was associated with higher Child-Pugh score. This could be explained
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35 by the presence of ascites as one of its subjective components; however, it was also linked
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37 to advanced stage of cirrhosis and higher rate of post-TIPS HE. Previous evidence
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39 supporting the use of TIPS in patients with recurrent ascites, along with our worse
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41 outcomes in patients with advanced cirrhosis and refractory ascites, show that covered
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43 TIPS should be used as first-line intervention in patients with cirrhosis and not just
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45 refractory but also recurrent ascites.
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53 Likewise, variceal bleeding as an indication for TIPS was associated with a reduction
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55 in post-procedure hospital care, without significant differences in follow-up compared
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57 with other indications. The urgency of the procedure, together with the lower stage of
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cirrhosis in this group, may have a bearing on this improved post-TIPS course of the disease.

As the main precipitants of TIPS, ascites and variceal bleeding incidence decreased substantially after shunt creation. Furthermore, we observed a non-statistically significant reduction in episodes of HRS and spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (SBP). As expected from previous studies [8-9], the HE rate significantly increased; nonetheless, this was easily managed with pharmacological treatment in all patients and no TIPS closures were required. **Factors associated with a lower risk of post-TIPS HE were again the indication of variceal bleeding and a reduced stage of cirrhosis, supporting early use of TIPS to avoid its more frequent complications.**

Additionally, in agreement with other results [25-28], TIPS has been shown to improve both hepatic and renal function and normalize hyponatremia. In an interesting finding, hemoglobin levels have been shown to rise after TIPS placement, which may point to another indication for TIPS in less common PH complications such as chronic anemia due to PHG and gastric antral vascular ectasia, with their associated health care burden.

One limitation of the present study was its observational and retrospective methodology, which tends towards information bias and confounding variables. We attempted to diminish potential confounding factors by carefully and reliably reviewing medical records and conducting multivariate analyses. Secondly, the long inclusion period may imply changes in TIPS technique over time, although the success rates and complications related to the procedure were similar to previous studies [22-24]. Moreover, more experienced radiologists and optimal candidate selection have been associated with a decrease in the rate of complications and increased use over time.

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In summary, TIPS influences the clinical course of cirrhosis by reducing the number of emergency department visits and hospital admissions. In our cohort, TIPS was a safe procedure with a high success rate that led to a reduction of most PH-related complications, along with an improvement in hepatic and renal function, hyponatremia and anemia. Variceal bleeding as the indication for TIPS, together with a prompt procedure in patients with early stage cirrhosis, was associated with a lower post-TIPS hospital care burden. This indicates a key role for TIPS, particularly in the early stages of cirrhosis, which may provide a window of opportunity to modify the natural history of the disease.

In our view the results of this study could have an important impact on clinical practice. We propose earlier and expanded considerations of TIPS for managing PH-related complications as a strategy to reduce hospital-based care in this group of patients.

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Figures

- Figure 1. Boxplot showing variations in MELD (A) and Child-Pugh (B) scores over the first year after TIPS placement: paired samples t-test.

Supplementary figures:

- Supplementary figure 1. Time of follow-up from first decompensation to TIPS creation (A) and from procedure to the end of the study (B).

Tables

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- Table 2. Pre- and post-TIPS complications of cirrhosis: McNemar test.
- Table 3. Laboratory baseline levels and variations over the first year after TIPS placement: paired samples t-test and Wilcoxon test.
- Table 4. Characteristics of study population according to post-TIPS hospital care: univariate analysis.
- Table 5. Predictive factors of post-TIPS medical care: multivariate logistic regression analysis.

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Figure 1. Boxplot showing variations in MELD (A) and Child-Pugh (B) scores over the first year after TIPS placement: paired samples t-test.

A

B

Figure 1. Boxplot showing variations in MELD (A) and Child-Pugh (B) scores over the first year after TIPS placement: paired samples t-test.

A

B

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of study patients.

Measure	Patients (n=104)
Age (y), mean (SD)	60 (10)
Sex, n (%)	
- Male	75 (72)
- Female	29 (28)
Etiology, n (%)	
- Alcohol	56 (54)
- HCV or HBV	15 (14)
- Alcohol and HCV	19 (18)
- Other*	14 (14)
Disease duration before TIPS (y), median (IQR)	3 (0-8)
MELD score, mean (SD)	14 (5)
Child-Pugh score, mean (SD)	8 (2)
Indication for TIPS, n (%)	
- Refractory ascites	52 (50)
- Variceal bleeding	40 (39)
- Hepatic hydrothorax	6 (6)
- Other**	6 (6)
Echocardiogram, mean (SD)	
- Ejection fraction of the left ventricle (%)	70 (7)
- Pulmonary artery pressure (mmHg)	33 (7)
- E/A ratio	0.98 (0.3)

Abbreviations: Hepatitis C Virus (HCV); Hepatitis B Virus (HBV), Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt (TIPS).

* Non-alcoholic steatohepatitis, cholestatic liver disease, autoimmune liver disease, hemochromatosis or cryptogenic liver disease.

** Portal vein thrombosis, hepatorenal syndrome and prophylaxis of complications of abdominal surgery.

Table 2. Pre- and post-TIPS complications of cirrhosis: McNemar test.

Complications of cirrhosis, n (%)	Pre-TIPS	Post-TIPS	<i>p</i> value
Ascites	78 (75)	41 (40)	<0.001
Variceal bleeding	51 (49)	7 (7)	<0.001
Hepatic encephalopathy	24 (23)	55 (53)	<0.001
Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis	19 (18)	10 (10)	0.108
Hepatorenal syndrome	17 (16)	14 (14)	0.664
Hepatic hydrothorax	7 (7)	3 (3)	0.344
<i>Acute-on-chronic liver failure</i>	<i>3 (3)</i>	<i>10 (10)</i>	<i>0.092</i>
Hepatocellular carcinoma	3 (3)	16 (15)	<0.001

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Table 2. Pre- and post-TIPS complications of cirrhosis: McNemar test.

Complications of cirrhosis, n (%)	Pre-TIPS	Post-TIPS	<i>p</i> value
Ascites	78 (75)	41 (40)	<0.001
Variceal bleeding	51 (49)	7 (7)	<0.001
Hepatic encephalopathy	24 (23)	55 (53)	<0.001
Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis	19 (18)	10 (10)	0.108
Hepatorenal syndrome	17 (16)	14 (14)	0.664
Hepatic hydrothorax	7 (7)	3 (3)	0.344
Acute-on-chronic liver failure	3 (3)	10 (10)	0.092
Hepatocellular carcinoma	3 (3)	16 (15)	<0.001

Table 3. Laboratory baseline levels and variations over the first year after TIPS placement: paired samples t-test and Wilcoxon test.

Parameter, Mean (SD)	Pre-TIPS (n=104)	<1 month (n=104)	6 months (n=67)	1 year (n=57)
Creatinine (mg/dl)	1.1 (0.7)	1.0 (0.7)*	0.9 (0.4)*	0.9 (0.7)
Sodium (mEq/L)	134 (7.3)	136 (6.9)**	137 (5.5)***	138 (3.8)***
Albumin (g/dL)	3.1 (0.7)	2.9 (0.6)*	3.2 (0.6)	3.3 (0.7)
Bilirubin (mg/dL)	2.5 (2.8)	3.4 (3.1)**	3.0 (3.4)**	2.4 (2.9)
International Normalized Ratio	1.4 (0.5)	1.5 (0.4)*	1.4 (0.3)	1.3 (0.3)
Quick index (%)	63 (19.4)	57 (17.3)***	66 (13.9)	70 (14.4)
Aspartate aminotransferase (IU/L)	66 (77.9)	135 (299)*	56 (38.6)	45 (24.2)
Alanine aminotransferase (IU/L)	41 (65.1)	98 (175)**	31 (23.7)	29.4 (16.5)
Gamma-glutamyl transferase (IU/L)	115 (121)	119 (115)	134 (165)	101 (85)*
Alkaline phosphatase (IU/L)	196 (159)	227 (156)***	210 (117)	190 (103)
Hemoglobin (g/dl)	9.6 (2.3)	10.3 (8.5)	11.1 (2.3)**	11.4 (2.6)**
Platelets ($\times 10^9/L$)	124209 (90297)	109757 (70466)	118224 (58388)	120894 (54997)

*p <0.05

**p <0.005

***p <0.001

Table 4. Characteristics of study population according to post-TIPS hospital care: univariate analysis.

Measure	Post-TIPS emergency department visits			Post-TIPS hospital admissions		
	Yes (n=66)	No (n=38)	p value	Yes (n=60)	No (n=44)	p value
Age (y), mean (SD)	61 (10)	58 (10)	0.258	61 (10)	57 (10)	0.044
Sex, n (%)			0.275			0.444
- Male	50 (67)	25 (33)		45 (60)	30 (40)	
- Female	16 (55)	13 (44)		15 (52)	14 (48)	
Etiology, n (%)						
- Alcohol	29 (44)	27 (71)	0.008	27 (45)	29 (66)	0.035
- HCV or HBV	10 (15)	5 (13)	0.781	10 (17)	5 (11)	0.447
- Alcohol and HCV	16 (24)	3 (8)	0.038	13 (22)	6 (14)	0.295
- Other*	11 (17)	3 (8)	0.207	10 (17)	4 (9)	0.263
Etiological treatment, n (%)	33 (50)	14 (37)	0.327	28 (47)	19 (43)	0.903
First decompensation, n (%)						
- Ascites	37 (57)	13 (32)	0.017	32 (53)	18 (41)	0.200
- Variceal bleeding	19 (29)	21 (54)	0.011	21 (35)	19 (43)	0.394
- Hepatic encephalopathy	6 (10)	0 (0)	0.082	5 (9)	1 (2)	0.396
- Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis	1 (2)	3 (8)	0.142	1 (2)	3 (7)	0.307
- Hepatic hydrothorax	1 (2)	1 (3)	1.000	0 (0)	2 (5)	0.174
- Liver failure	1 (2)	1 (3)	1.000	1 (2)	1 (2)	1.000
Duration from first decompensation to TIPS (m), median (IQR)	10 (5-37)	3 (0-15)	0.093	10 (4-37)	5 (0-23)	0.058
MELD score, mean (SD)	14 (5)	14 (6)	0.877	14 (5)	14 (6)	0.524
Child-Pugh score, mean (SD)	8 (2)	8 (2)	0.304	8 (2)	8 (2)	0.323
Stages of cirrhosis, n (%)						
- 3	8 (12)	12 (32)	0.015	11 (18)	9 (20)	0.786
- 4	8 (12)	5 (13)	0.878	7 (12)	6 (14)	0.764
- 5	50 (76)	21 (55)	0.031	42 (70)	29 (66)	0.658
Indication for TIPS, n (%)						
- Refractory ascites	41 (61)	11 (29)	0.001	35 (58)	17 (39)	0.047
- Variceal bleeding	15 (23)	25 (66)	0.000	16 (27)	24 (55)	0.004
- Hepatic hydrothorax	5 (8)	1 (3)	0.412	4 (7)	2 (5)	1.000
- Other**	5 (8)	1 (3)	0.412	5 (8)	1 (2)	0.397
Procedure urgency, n (%)			0.000			0.042
- Urgent	15 (39)	23 (61)		17 (45)	21 (55)	
- Elective	51 (77)	15 (23)		43 (65)	23 (35)	
Portosystemic gradient pressure, mean (SD)						
- Pre-TIPS	20 (5)	20 (6)	0.820	20 (4)	20 (6)	1.000
- Post-TIPS	8 (2)	8 (2)	0.268	8 (2)	8 (2)	0.183
TIPS effectiveness, n (%)						
- Hemodynamic	54 (98)	30 (97)	---	49 (98)	35 (97)	1.000
- Clinical	59 (89)	37 (97)	0.142	53 (88)	43 (98)	0.134
Complications, n (%)						
- <u>Technical</u>	<u>2 (3)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>---</u>	<u>2 (3)</u>	<u>0 (0)</u>	<u>---</u>
- <u>Shunt-related</u>	<u>15 (23)</u>	<u>4 (11)</u>	<u>0.121</u>	<u>13 (22)</u>	<u>6 (14)</u>	<u>0.295</u>
- <u>Shunt dysfunction</u>	<u>13 (20)</u>	<u>4 (11)</u>	<u>0.223</u>	<u>12 (20)</u>	<u>5 (11)</u>	<u>0.239</u>

Abbreviations: Hepatitis C Virus (HCV); Hepatitis B Virus (HBV), Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt (TIPS).

* Non-alcoholic steatohepatitis. cholestatic liver disease. autoimmune liver disease. hemochromatosis or cryptogenic liver disease.

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Abbreviations: Hepatitis C Virus (HCV); Hepatitis B Virus (HBV), Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt (TIPS).

* Non-alcoholic steatohepatitis. cholestatic liver disease. autoimmune liver disease. hemochromatosis or cryptogenic liver disease.

** Portal vein thrombosis. hepatorenal syndrome and prophylaxis of complications of abdominal surgery.

Table 5. Predictive factors of post-TIPS medical care: multivariate logistic regression analysis.

Measure	Post-TIPS emergency department visits		Post-TIPS hospital admissions	
	OR (95CI)	p-value	OR (95CI)	p-value
Age	---	---	0.965 (0.922-1.01)	0.115
Etiology				
- Alcohol	0.327 (0.103-1.04)	0.057	0.437 (0.19-1.03)	0.060
- Alcohol and HCV	3.132 (0.54-18.07)	0.202	---	---
Stages of cirrhosis			---	---
- 3	1.745 (0.30-10.17)	0.536		
- 5	0.452 (0.07-2.97)	0.409		
Indication for TIPS				
- Refractory ascites	0.891 (0.15-5.18)	0.898	0.759 (0.17-3.32)	0.714
- Variceal bleeding	0.047 (0.006-0.39)	0.005	0.234 (0.05-1.05)	0.058

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Article title Transjugular Intrahepatic Portosystemic Shunt Reduces Hospital Assistance Requirements in patients with Cirrhosis.

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Herewith I confirm, on behalf of all authors, that the information provided is accurate.

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